

Description.

In the following proof:

n is a natural number ≥ 3

p, q are both odd primes such that $2 < p \leq q < 2n - 2$,

k_0 is a natural number ≥ 3

p_0, q_0 are odd primes such that $2 < p_0 \leq q_0 < 2k_0 - 2$

t is a natural number ≥ 0 , p_c indicates a natural number that can be composite or even prime with the same interval limitations as p_0 and q_0 , and the indicator number with "d" is revealed during the proof.

Statement:

Every even number $2n \geq 6$ can always be written as the sum of two odd primes, that is, the form $2n = p + q$ always exists.

Proof by contradiction.

Let there be hypothetically at least one $2k_0$ that cannot be expressed as $p_0 + q_0$, both odd primes. That is, for every prime or composite p_c less than $2k_0 - 2$, its difference from $2k_0$ is always a composite. Then the consequence is that $2k_0 > p_0 + 8(t + 1)$ for every $t \geq 0$, making this number in fact greater than any odd given by the inequality, arriving at an absurdity.

Since there is always a p_0 such that $2 < p_0 < 2k_0 - 2$, we can write:

$2k_0 = p_0 + d$, with d odd composite for every p_0 less than $2k_0 - 2$. Now, since the smallest odd composite is $d = 9$, it follows that the possible minimum value for $2k_0$ is $p_0 + 9$. In particular, substituting for p_0 the minimum value 3, we see that the smallest value in absolute terms is 12.

Therefore $2k_0 > p_0 + 8$, and the inequality is verified for $t = 0$. We continue by induction, assuming the inequality is true for the generic t , deducing that it is also true for $t + 1$.

Given that $2k_0$ is greater than $p_0 + 8(t + 1) + 2$ (and therefore the same inequality holds without $(+2)$)*, since the condition $p_c + d = p_c + 9$ must be respected, it follows that the value minimum is:

$$2k_0 = p_0 + 8(t + 1) + 9 = p_0 + 8t + 8 + 8 + 1 = p_0 + 8(t + 1 + 1) + 1.$$

Therefore $2k_0$ is strictly greater than $p_0 + 8(t + 1 + 1)$, where this time instead of t we have $t + 1$.

C.v.d.

*Let's make sure that

$$p_0 + 8t + 8 + 1 = A$$

can be written as the sum of two odd primes less than that value minus 2. Let's proceed by contradiction that it cannot be.

Let's rewrite the number above as follows:

$$p_0 + 8t + 9 = p_0 + 8t + 6 + 3.$$

Every unordered pair of odd

(a_0, b_0) , such that $a_0 + b_0 = A$, has at least one of the terms of the pair composite. But the smallest odd composite is 9, so all pairs are of the type $(a_0, 9+)$, by the absurd hypothesis (9+ is an odd composite greater than or equal to 9). But then the number $p_0 + 8t + 6$ is also distant from A by an amount of at least 9. Assuming it is precisely 9, it is easily seen that $3 = 9$, ($3 = 9+$), arriving at an absurdity.